

Battlefield Damage Assessment & Repair: Live Firing Trials - 1987

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Abstract

International (U.S., United Kingdom (UK), and Federal Republic of Germany (FRG)) Battlefield Damage Assessment and Repair (BDAR) Live Firing Trials were held from 7 to 29 July 1987 at Meppen, Germany. The trials were successfully completed with all objectives accomplished. The trials involved exposing eight pieces of equipment to indirect fire, direct fire, antitank mines, and charges which simulated the free air blast effect of typical threat munitions. After each firing, technical firing data were collected, an assessment of the damage was made, and expedient repairs were made on the target equipment. More than 90 percent of all critical damages were repaired during the trials. Several combat enhancements were utilized on various pieces of target equipment and their effectiveness was recorded.

Introduction

The FRG has been conducting independent BDAR field trials for six years. In 1985, the FRG Ministry of Defence (MOD) invited the U.S. to join them in the 1986 Field Trials to be conducted at the Meppen, Germany, test facility. This invitation was accepted and the U.S. participated in the first multinational BDAR field trial. This trial involved the exposure of four types of equipment to statically detonated artillery rounds (155mm) and the application of BDAR repair procedures.

An invitation was again extended by the German MOD in 1986 to participate in the 1987 field trials, and this time the invitation was accepted by both the U.S. and the UK. A test plan for the U.S. participation was prepared jointly by the U.S. Army Materiel Systems Analysis Activity (AMSAA) and the Ballistic Research Laboratory (BRL) (Reference 1). Six agencies participated in the trials along with an eight soldier photographic team and thirty-two soldiers (crews and mechanics). Project management was again provided by AMSAA which maintained the test records jointly with BRL, the Tank Automotive Command (TACOM), the Troop Support Command (TROSCOM), and the U.S. Army Ordnance Center and School (USAOC&S). The test report was issued by AMSAA (Reference 2).

Objectives

U.S. objectives of this field trial were determined by the office of the DA Deputy Chief of Staff for Logistics. The objectives were:

1. Enhance interoperability (to include BDAR and recovery).
2. Provide hands-on BDAR training and assessment of such training.
3. Produce BDAR training materiel, including visual training aids.
4. Aid in the development/verification of doctrine and TM's.
5. Provide opportunity for U.S. Reserve Component Training.
6. Support design of new systems.
7. Support improvements through design or reconfiguration of existing systems.

Scope of Tests

The firing trial consisted of three types of firings: indirect, antitank mines, and direct. The indirect firings involved arraying a variety of U.S. equipment at various distances from the 155mm artillery round. The round was statically detonated and was placed so as to maximize fragmentation spray on the target equipment.

The antitank mine firings were directed against the suspension system of the M60A3 tank. The mines were placed just behind the number one road wheel. The direct firings were directed against the right center of the M60A3 turret.

Target Equipment

Eight types of target equipment were provided by USAREUR, TACOM, and Natick Laboratory. The equipment was:

- M60A3 Main Battle Tank (MBT)
- M901 Improved TOW Vehicle (ITV)
- M577 Command Track
- High Mobility Multipurpose Wheeled Vehicle (HMMWV)
- 15KW Motor Generator
- 5KW Motor Generator
- S-250/G Shelter
- S-280 Hardened Tactical Shelter (HATS)

Equipment fuel tanks were kept between 1/2 and 3/4 full. No ammunition or personnel dummies were used. The vehicles were driven approximately 10 miles to the indirect fire range or 1/2 mile to the direct fire range. Both generators were operational and produced power. The engines on the TACOM equipment were left running during the detonation.

M60A3 (TTS) Main Battle Tank

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M901A1 Improved TOW Vehicle

15 kw and 5 kw Motor Generators

M577 Command Track

S250/G Shelter

High Mobility Multi-Purpose Wheeled Vehicle

Test Munitions

The munitions were provided by the Meppen test facility and 200th TAMMC. They consisted of:

- o 8 rounds of L15A1, 155mm artillery projectiles
- o 2 DM-11 antitank mines
- o 5 rounds of DM-101, 20mm Armor Piercing High Explosive (APHE)
- o 5 rounds of DM-81, 40mm High Explosive (HE)
- o 2 high explosive charges
 - 1.5 kg Pentaerythritetranitrat (PETN)
 - 3.0 kg PETN
- o 6 rounds of 105MM High Explosive Antitank (HEAT)

The L15A1 has a greater charge, is taller, and has thinner walls than the German DM21, 155mm round. It produces smaller, more uniform fragments traveling at greater velocity (see Figures 1 and 2). This round was used because it provided a greater probability of having its fragments actually striking the target equipment. The two plastic explosive charges were used to simulate the free air blast effect of the 125mm projectile and the TOW missile.

The desire was to create repairable damage, not catastrophic damage. Distances and the presentation of the targets along with the characteristics of the munitions were calculated with this objective in mind.

Test Ranges

The indirect fire test range is located on an open flat area. The 155mm round was placed at the apex of a 360 degree circle with the equipment arrayed around it at various distances and angles from the projectile (see Figure 3). The projectile was placed nose up on top of a post in order to provide maximum fragmentation spray against the target equipment. The round was statically detonated from a blockhouse located 120 M north of the apex.

Figure 4 provides the layout of the range for the two aerial bursts. The projectile was suspended on its side from a scaffold whose height was dependent on the amount of damage desired. For the first aerial firing, the projectile was 8.3 M above the

Figure 1. Sketch Showing External and Sectioned Views of the UK L15A1 Projectile.

Figure 2. Sketch Showing External and Sectioned Views of the FRG DM21 Projectile.

PLAN VIEW OF TARGET VEHICLES ARRANGED FOR INDIRECT FIRING ROUND NUMBER 1

Figure 3. Typical Indirect Fire Target Array.

ground and for the second firing was 6.3 M above the ground.

The antitank mine firings were conducted within a small flat area with a semi-circular dirt berm around it. The mine was placed in a hole underneath the track and then statically detonated.

Figure 5 shows an M60A3 MBT within the direct fire range. The 20mm APHE and the 40mm rounds were fired at the targets from guns. The simulated firings (125mm and TOW) were statically detonated from a bunker located 100 M to the south of the target.

Summary of Tests

The firings are summarized in the following Table.

- The table shows:
- Each piece of target equipment
 - The firing date
 - The shot number
 - The munitions used
 - Exposure (orientation of the target)
 - The distance of the equipment from the munitions

Post Firing Procedure

After each firing the following actions took place:

Documentation

Technical inspections were performed to observe and document damage, utilizing EPADDS forms and the proposed BDAR forms designed by the USAOC&S. Camera

ARRANGEMENT OF TARGET VEHICLES FOR OVERHEAD DETONATION OF ARTILLERY PROJECTILE, ROUND NO. 14

DATE: 27 JULY TIME: 0955

Figure 4. Typical Overhead Detonation Target Array.

Table . TOTAL NUMBER OF FIRINGS ON EACH OF THE INDIVIDUAL US TARGET SYSTEMS

July Date	Shot Numbers	Munition(s)	Exposures	Ranges
① M 60 A 3				
13	1	L15A1	Left Side	7 m
14	3	L15A1	Right Side	7 m
22	10	L15A1	Right Side	5 m
23	12	L15A1	Aerial Burst (Turret)	5 m
27	14	L15A1	Aerial Burst (Turret)	3 m
② M 60 A 3				
14	4	20mm APHEL, 5 Rds.	Right Turret	Contact
15	6	40mm HE, 5 Rds.	Right Turret	Contact
13	2	Anti-Tank Mine	Right Front Track	Contact
24	13	Anti-Tank Mine	Left Front Track	Contact
21	8	1.5 kg Explosive Charge	Right Turret	"Contact"
23	11	3.0 kg Explosive Charge	Right Turret	"Contact"
① M 113 (M 577)				
14	3	L15A1	Left Side	10 m
15	5	L15A1	Right Side	10 m
22	10	L15A1	45° Right Side	10 m
② M 113 (M 901)				
14	3	L15A1	Left Side	10 m
15	5	L15A1	Right Side	10 m
21	9	L15A1	45° Left Side	10 m
① HMMWV (with Special Radiator)				
13	1	L15A1	Front	20 m
15	5	L15A1	Front	20 m
21	9	L15A1	45° Left Side	20 m
27	14	L15A1	Aerial Burst	17 m
② HMMWV				
14	3	L15A1	Front	20 m
16	7	L15A1	Left Side	20 m
22	10	L15A1	Right Side	20 m
① Electronics Shelter (Conventional)				
14	3	L15A1	Right Side	20 m
16	7	L15A1	Left Side	25 m
23	12	L15A1	Above and Front	20 m
27	14	L15A1	Above and Front	17 m
② Electronics Shelter (with Kevlar Panels)				
13	1	L15A1	Left Side	20 m
15	5	L15A1	Right Side	20 m
21	9	L15A1	Front	20 m
● 15 KW Motor-Generator Set				
15	5	L15A1	Right Side	20 m
16	7	L15A1	Left Side	20 m
21	9	L15A1	Right Side	20 m
● 5 KW Motor-Generator Set				
14	3	L15A1	Left Side	20 m
16	7	L15A1	Right Side	20 m
22	10	L15A1	Right Side	20 m

The next day's schedule
 Maintenance concerns
 Administrative matters

Test Results

Damage to the following critical components was recorded:

- M60A3 Support roller hub covers, support roller bearings, bore evacuator, shock absorbers, thermal sight, laser range finder, grenade power box, stabilization shut off switch, road wheel, road wheel arm, torsion bar, track shoes, ammunition select switch, vision blocks, XM21 computer output unit, electrical cables
- M901/M577 Radiator hose, radiator, final drive, fuel cell
- HMMWV Radiator hose, tires, battery, differential, radiator, oil cooler, oil pan, output gear box, valve cover, control box, fuel tank, transmission
- 15KW, 5KW Engine block, fuel filter, wiring harness, resistors, terminal board, generator housing

Reference 2 details the damages by shot, describes the repair procedures employed, lists repair time, materials used, pre- and post-BDAR status, repair level, and results of the repair actions.

Figure 5. M60A3(TTS) MBT on Direct Fire Range.

crews recorded damage and assessment and repair procedures using still photos and video recorders. Survivability enhancements were examined, evaluated, and documented.

BDAR

The operator, organizational maintenance, and intermediate direct support maintenance teams assessed and attempted to repair the equipment in turn. Equipment was classified into one of four categories before effecting repairs and after the repairs were made. The categories were:

Fully Mission Capable - The equipment can perform all missions safely without operational limitations or inspection faults.

Combat Capable - The equipment meets the minimum functional combat capability (MFCC) criteria.

Combat Emergency Capable - Functionally adequate for specific combat missions.

Self-recovery Capable - Adequate mobility for self-recovery; may involve hazardous conditions.

The equipment was repaired on the range if possible. If it could not be repaired on the range, then it was towed back to a maintenance point. Repair work was performed at as low a level as possible. Still cameras and video equipment were utilized to record the repair procedures.

After repair, an operational check was made on all systems on the equipment. Vehicles were test driven 20 KM if the nature of the damage warranted it.

Debriefing Meeting - Summary of the Day's Activities

On Monday through Thursday, at 1800 hrs, a meeting was conducted by the field trials Officer in Charge (OIC). The day's activities were discussed in order to disseminate repair information and to adjust the next day's firings, if necessary.

Specifically, the joint (UK, US, FRG) group discussed:

- Damage observed on each piece of equipment
- BDAR methods employed
- Equipment availability

Typical Repairs

<u>Type of Damage</u>	<u>Repair Technique</u>
Wiring	Splicing
Cracks or holes in casings	Cold steel, welding
Fuel tank	Screw and tape
Loose prisms	Gluing
Radiator/oil cooler damage	Replacement, soldering
Control box	Shorting around affected circuits
Radiator hose (metal)	Welding

Vulnerability Observations

The nature of the trials, the limitations imposed, and the fact that fragmentation spray cannot be predicted accurately enough to know what areas on the targets would be struck, all impacted on the types of damage found. For instance, because of the restriction on creating catastrophic damage, penetration of the hull of the M60A3 to damage wiring harnesses could not be attempted. Due to the short duration of the trials, damages had to be maximized from each firing. Utilizing Warsaw Pact munitions IAW Soviet doctrine would probably not create the same damages found during the trials. Again, the principal purpose was to create damage for repair, not simulate expected damage. The use of lethality and probability of hit models is a critical after action process in order to put the trial results in perspective.

BDAR Observations

The soldiers involved in the field trials quickly became proficient in applying BDAR fixes to the types of damage found during the firings. Initially, the soldiers displayed a hesitancy in applying field expedients due to the shock of seeing combat-type damage, and the impact of the school training that they had received (reinforced daily at their unit) to utilize only normal (TM) repair procedures. The bulk of the repair work involved welding, brazing, cutting, and replacement of parts.

While the Army is incorporating simulators in

its BDAR training, the soldiers also need to see combat damage on actual vehicles which will show them that the expedient repairs they are learning really can be applied.

Three video film crews and a still photographer were used to document the field trials. The video films were given to the USAOC&S to be edited and made into a BDAR training film. The film should be completed in February 1988.

Utilizing modified DA Form 2404 (Equipment Inspection and Maintenance Worksheet), the soldiers were able to quickly annotate the damages found. However, they must be fully trained in the use of the form as there was a tendency to record minimal information. The advantages of using this form, with which they are familiar and which has line drawings of their equipment on it, outweigh the disadvantages of having to maintain and control extra forms and conduct extra training on their use.

Conclusions and Recommendations

During the course of the field trials, all of the objectives listed at the beginning of this paper were met. The trials clearly demonstrated the necessity of allowing BDAR-type repairs in a combat environment.

While the trials were very limited in scope and in the damages found, the repair procedures in the BDAR manuals and technical manuals appeared to have only minor deficiencies.

The U.S. BDAR teams demonstrated the ability to maintain a high rate of success in repair work through the use of expedient repairs. This was in an environment where there were few spare parts, equipment, or consumables.

Because the scope of the trials was limited in the number and type of firings, the nature of the damage (no catastrophic damage), and the type of ammunition used, the results were also limited. It should be pointed out that last year there were only four types of U.S. equipment exposed to indirect firing. This year, the U.S. participation was expanded to include eight types of equipment exposed to indirect, direct, and antitank mine firings.

With respect to vulnerability/survivability related observations, the 1987 Trials demonstrated the impact of BDAR repairs upon combat resilience (as called for in Reference 4). Recognizing that the field trials did not utilize Warsaw Pact ammunition, and that the ammunition used for indirect fire was positioned to obtain the greatest possible fragmentation spray, certain experimental survivability enhancements had promising results. They were:

- o The use of quick change core radiators and oil coolers. The cores were easily changed on a tactical vehicle by the operator in only one minute. This is normally performed by intermediate forward maintenance personnel, and takes a minimum of 30 minutes to accomplish.
- o The laminated windshield in the HMMWV prevented all fragmentation hitting it from entering the crew compartment.

Standardization of radiator lines and hydraulic lines would ease problems in cross-leveling of spare parts between pieces of equipment.

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Biography

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M60A3 (TTS) Antitank Mine Damage

Typical M60A3 (TTS) Sight Damage

M113 FOV Road Wheel Hub Protector
Fragmentation Damage

Aerial Burst Gallows

15 kw Motor Generator Wiring Fragmentation Damage

Typical Metal Line Damage

3 kg Simulated Charge Against an M60A3 (TTS) Turret

Typical Road Wheel Hub Cap Damage